

ELECTROSPUN NANOFIBROUS COMPOSITES TO CONTROL DRUG RELEASE AND INTERACTION BETWEEN HYDROPHILIC DRUG AND HYDROPHOBIC BLENDED POLYMER MATRIX

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Abstract

This study has developed new electrospun hybrid nanocomposite systems using poly(lactic acid) PLA: poly(ϵ -caprolactone) PCL blends and PLA: PCL / halloysite nanotubes-3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (HNT-ASP) to take the advantage of the sustained release of hydrophilic drug tetracycline hydrochloride (TCH) from hydrophobic PLA: PCL composite system. The impact of interaction between the two typical drugs, namely TCH and Indomethacin (IMC), and PLA: PCL blends on the drug release was examined. The study also investigated the drug release kinetics by fitting the experimental release data with five mathematical models for drug delivery. The average nanofiber diameters were found to be significantly reduced when increasing the TCH concentration due to the enhancement of solution electrical conductivity in contrast to the presence of IMC. The addition of both TCH and IMC drugs to PLA: PCL blends reduce the crystallinity level, glass transition temperature T_g and melting temperature T_m values of PCL within the blends. The reduction of drug release and elimination of the impairment of the interaction between the polymer and drug were achieved by mobilizing TCH into HNT-ASP to be then embedded in the PLA: PCL nanofibers. The typical characteristic was clearly revealed with excellent agreement between obtained experimental data and Ritger-peppas and Zeng models in drug release kinetics.

1 Introduction

Electrospinning method has been recently used to fabricate hybrid fiber mats based on polymer nanocomposites. Polymer nanocomposites by

incorporating nanoparticles have attracted a great attention due to their excellent tailored multifunctional properties [1] and their unique structures which may not be accomplished by conventional composites [2]. Halloysite nanotubes (HNTs) have also been focused on as cost-effective nanoparticles for the reinforcement purpose. Poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) is a hydrophobic and semi-crystalline polymer [3] without generating local acidic environment after the PCL degradation. Poly(lactic acid) (PLA) has favourable material properties, including easy processability, dissolvability in common solvents, good sustainability and biocompatibility [4]. PLA with the amorphous phase can degrade to form nontoxic monomers for the biomedical application. It submits secession to monomeric units of lactic acid in the body, which is naturally in the carbohydrate metabolism [5, 6]. Furthermore, PCL is a slowly degraded biopolymer compared with many other counterparts such as PLA due to its semi-crystalline nature [7]. Moreover, it is not harmful to local tissues because it does not form a similar acidic environment to poly(lactide-co-glycolide) (PLGA) or PLA. In the past decades, scientists concentrated on the use of polymers as a carrier and release controller for drug delivery systems owing to the enhancement of healing effectiveness and decrease of toxic side-effects [8]. In addition, the interaction between drug and carrier is very critical to manage a sustained drug release [9]. Hydrophobic drugs including clindamycin, ciprofloxacin, and cephalexin can be simply incorporated and interacted with hydrophobic polymers. However, hydrophilic drugs cannot be embedded into hydrophobic polymers due to their weak interactions

and the drug release rate may not be well controlled [10].

The aim of this study is to create a novel electrospun hybrid composite structure by combining PLA: PCL blends with ASP, which is then employed to form a novel drug delivery system. This system can overcome a poor interaction between TCH and the carrier when compared with IMC. The major emphasis was on a holistic investigation of fabrication process, material characterization, drug release tests and release kinetic modelling of such hybrid composites.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

PLA (molecular weight (MW) = 93,500 g/mol), PCL (MW = 80,000 g/mol) and HNT modifier ASP, TCH (TCH, $C_{22}H_{24}N_2O_8 \cdot HCl$, MW = 480.9 g/mol) and IMC ($C_{19}H_{16}ClNO_4$, MW = 357.79 g/mol) drugs, phosphate buffer solution (PBS) as drug-release medium and chloroform and methanol solvents, were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Ltd, Australia. Halloysite nanotubes (HNTs) were obtained from Imerys Tableware Limited, New Zealand.

2.2 Electrospinning

TCH and IMC with concentration 5 wt%/v were initially mixed with blend solution (PLA: PCL at a mix ratio of 1:1), where TCH was mixed with 1 wt%/v HNT-ASP and then it was added to PLA: PCL solution. In the further electrospinning step, the different types of solutions were transferred to a 10-ml syringe pump (A Fusion 100 syringe pump, Chemyx Inc. Stafford, TX USA). The flow rate of solution was set to 2 ml/h, and the applied voltage was in the range of 25–28 kV. The needle-to-collector distance was 13cm. The electrospinning process was carried out at 24°C, and the resulting fibers were collected on a mesh collector covered with flat aluminium foil. The thickness of fiber mat produced was measured using a micrometer, and was in the range from 330 to 450 μm . The release amounts of TCH and IMC in PBS were determined

by a UV–vis spectrophotometer. The drug release data were fitted to five conventional mathematical models [11] for kinetics of drug release including zero order, first order, Higuchi, Ritger-Peppas and newly developed Zeng model [9].

2.3 In vitro drug release study

The drug-loaded fiber mat sample (2 cm \times 2 cm) was incubated in 20 ml PBS (pH=7.4) using a rotary shaker at 37°C. After the required incubation time for drug release, the sample was transferred to 20 ml fresh buffer solution and 36 separate incubations were done to obtain the TCH and IMC release data for the three different types of nanofiber mats and the released TCH amount in the buffer solution was determined afterwards.

2.4 Characterization techniques

The electrical conductivity and pH value of the solution were measured with the aid of a WP-81 Waterproof pH and Conductivity Meter (TPS, Australia). The morphology of electrospun nanofibers was studied via an EVO 40XVP scanning electron microscope (SEM) (Germany) at an accelerating voltage of 5 kV. Prior to the SEM observation, the samples were sputter-coated with platinum. Fiber diameter was calculated from the SEM images by using an imaging analysis tool in the Zeiss Smart SEM software. For each sample, measurements were made for a minimum of 150 fibers from multiple scanned SEM images at a rate of 15 fibers per image.

XRD measurements of prepared samples were performed in a Bruker Discover 8 X-ray diffractometer (Germany) in operation at 40 kV and 40 mA. The Cu-K α radiation was monochromatized with graphite sample monochromators in $2\theta = 5^\circ$ - 40° with a scanning rate of 0.05°/s. The d -spacing (d) was determined from Bragg's equation, $n\lambda = 2d\sin\theta$, where θ is the diffraction angle, λ is the wavelength ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$ for a Cu target), and n is an integer. The level of crystallinity was determined by applying the area integration method from XRD intensity data over the range of $2\theta = 8^\circ$ - 27° [12].

Thermal analysis was performed using a DSC6000 PerkinElmer (USA) with Cryofill liquid nitrogen

cooling system. Approximately 10 mg of cut fiber mat was sealed in an aluminium pan. The thermal behaviour was analyzed during the first heating scan between -90°C to 200°C with a ramp rate of $10^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was performed in a Spectrum 100 FTIR Spectrometer PerkinElmer (Japan). Spectra were recorded in range of $4000\text{--}550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with 4 cm^{-1} resolution by using an attenuated total reflectance (ATR) technique [13]. FTIR was used to investigate the interaction level between MPs and PLA: PCL blends.

The amount of TCH present in the release buffer was determined by a UV-vis spectrophotometer (JascoV-67) at wavelengths of 360 nm and 319 nm for TCH and IMC, respectively.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Effect of drug on fiber morphology

To investigate the effect of drug type, the PLA/PCL polymer solution was blended with IMC and TCH at 5wt%/v concentration. Figs. 1 and 2 demonstrate that the loaded IMC produced a uniform fibrous composite structure with much larger fiber diameters of 794 nm as opposed to TCH counterpart with fiber diameters of 623 nm. There was no remarkable change on the fiber diameters when adding IMC compared with PLA: PCL blend fibers. In addition, PLA: PCL/HNT-ASP/TCH composites also possess a uniform fibrous structure with a relatively small fiber diameter of 716 nm, in contrast to corresponding PLA: PCL blends and PLA: PCL/HNT-ASP composites.

The addition of IMC to PLA: PCL blend solution did not appear to significantly affect the solution electrical conductivity in good accordance with previous finding [14]. However, as expected, the use of cationic drug TCH further increases the solution conductivity.

Fig. 1. Micrographs of electrospun PLA: PCL based composites with: (a) IMC (b) TCH and (c) HNT-ASP /TCH. The scale bars represent $10\text{ }\mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 2. Effects of HNT-ASP, IMC and TCH on fiber diameters and solution electrical conductivity.

3.2 Crystallinity level and thermal properties

An XRD examination was carried out to investigate the impact of drug type on the crystallinity level and structures, after being loaded to the electrospun nanocomposites. The peaks in the pattern were labelled with the XRD reflection and the crystal planes (*hkl*) corresponding to the main crystalline peaks were directly detected in the DICVOL program of the FullProf software [15]. Fig 3 shows the XRD patterns for PLA: PCL blends and nanocomposite fibers loaded with TCH and IMC. The XRD patterns possess two diffraction peaks at angles of $2\theta = 20.11^{\circ}$ and 23.2° corresponding to the planes (101) and (200), respectively. There was no

significant difference in the peak positions for most samples, which indicates that the addition of TCH and IMC have very minor effect on the alteration of crystalline structures of electrospun composite fibers. This finding may reveal that the TCH and IMC are mostly dispersed in an amorphous state into the PLA: PCL nanofiber mat. This is due to the large surface area combined with small nanofibers in electrospinning induced quick solvent evaporation, which could provide a short period for drug recrystallization and formation of preferred configuration in amorphous state [16].

Fig. 3. XRD patterns for selected samples showing the relative position of the reflection peaks due to the addition of TCH and IMC drugs.

Fig. 4 demonstrates that the degree of crystallinity (X_c) of composites is reduced more remarkably when TCH is concurrently added as compared to that of PLA: PCL blends. Furthermore, IMC mixed with PLA: PCL blend has even more significant impact on the X_c than TCH based counterparts. The presence of both TCH and IMC appears to greatly accelerate the nucleation process. Accordingly, this phenomenon causes a shorter period than the required time for the disentanglement of molecular chains because the resulting degree of crystallinity is influenced by the restricted mobility of polymer chains, which prevents a more rapid growth of the developed crystals.

Fig. 4. Degree of crystallinity (X_c) results with additional TCH and IMC drugs.

Fig.5. DSC thermograms for selected material samples.

The DSC thermal properties of electrospun composite fibers with IMC and TCH drugs were shown in Table 1 and Fig 5. The glass transition temperature (T_g) of PCL within composites decreased considerably, and there was a slight decline in melting temperatures (T_m) of both PLA and PCL by embedding HNT-ASP with additional 5 wt%/v TCH. The decrease of T_g is ascribed to the low molecular weight of the drug TCH. The TCH molecules have short chains, which results in the decreased packing density of polymer chains, and thus facilitates the chain mobility leading to the lower T_g . Conversely, the use of TCH within composite fibers shows the significant increase of T_c at over 106°C as opposed to 84°C of PLA for PLA:

PCL blends. This finding implies that low molecular weight TCH can hinder the cold crystallization process of PLA, acting as an anti-nucleating agent, which, however, might behave as an opposite role of HNT-ASP. On the other hand, the loaded IMC led to a drop in the T_m , while there was a slight decrease in the crystallization temperature (T_c), arising from a better interaction between PLA: PCL blends relative to the used TCH.

Table 1: Thermal properties of PLA: PCL blend and PLA: PCL nanocomposites with TCH and IMC

Sample	T_g (°C) PCL	T_m (°C) PCL	T_c (°C) PLA	T_m (°C) PLA
PLA : PCL	-52.19	63.75	83.97	152.54
PLA: PCL/ IMC	-58.55	54.57	82.01	148.98
PLA : PCL/ TCH	-58.48	59.64	105.77	151.93
PLA: PCL/ HNT-ASP/ TCH	-61.43	59.17	102.77	149.07

3.3 FTIR evaluation

Fig.6 shows the FTIR spectra of PLA: PCL/TCH within nanocomposites and PLA: PCL/IMC system. The spectra of TCH within PLA: PCL blends and nanocomposites, were difficult to be assigned to the band shifting. However, the major noticeable change in the infrared spectra is that the bands of TCH at 1614 and 1581 cm^{-1} were observed within the nanocomposites, which are allocated to the C=O stretching at ring A and the C=O stretching at ring C, respectively. That confirms the successful encapsulation of TCH to nanocomposites. While, FT-IR spectra of PLA: PCL/ IMC demonstrated that the bonds existing at 1560 cm^{-1} associated with the ionization of carboxyl groups in the IMC, which also shows its effective encapsulation.

Fig. 6. FTIR spectra for selected material samples showing effect of drugs on the relative FTIR peaks.

3.4 In vitro drug release

The drug particles within polymer nanofibers have a tendency to stay on the fiber surface due to a fast solvent evaporation from PLA: PCL blend solution in electrospinning process and also high ionic interactions. Accordingly, a considerable burst release in the initial drug release is possible to take place. The burst release becomes quite large when it is not compatible between drug and PLA: PCL solution, as a result of their weak interaction. The release by using hydrophilic drug (TCH) to hydrophobic PLA: PCL blends was faster than that with hydrophobic drug (IMC). It can be seen from Fig. 7 that the drug release within the first 5 h is quite fast, particularly when using TCH drug (42% for PLA: PCL/ TCH vs. 30 % for PLA: PCL/ IMC). This can be attributed to the better interaction and compatibility between IMC and PLA: PCL blends compared with TCH. Furthermore, the chemical interaction between drug and its carrier can impede the drug crystallization within its carrier, which may then establish a sustained drug release in the crystalline state [17].

More evidently, the addition of 1 wt%/v HNT-ASP into PLA: PCL blends not only reduces the initial burst release to 30% after 5 h with reference to initial 42% for PLA: PCL blends, but also reveals a similar release trend in the duration of steady release period

from 50 h to 250 h, which implies the robust control of drug release for both short and long evaluation periods due to the use of HNT-ASP. HNTs have negative charge on the outer surface and positive charged on the inner surface [18]. The charges on the HNT-ASP may give rise to the electrostatic interaction between TCH and the outer surface and lumen of HNT-ASP, resulting in the reduction of TCH drug release from PLA: PCL/HNT-ASP nanocomposites.

Fig. 7. Drug release profiles for PLA: PCL loaded with IMC, TCH and HNT-ASP/TCH.

3.5 Release kinetics

The release kinetics was examined by fitting the drug release data to five mathematical models. Equations of these mathematical models and their reported parameters are listed in Table 1. The first order model shows that drug release rate completely relies on the drug concentration and its carrier. According to the n values of Ritger-Peppas model, the drug release mechanism follows the Fickian transport phenomenon [11] with a dominant diffusion process. However, according to Zeng model, the diffusion process and interaction between both drugs (TCH and IMC) and the carrier (PLA:PCL nanofibers) can make a significant impact on the drug release. IMC exhibits a much lower ΔG (i.e. the free energy variation between the free and bound states) [9] than TCH (-2.1×10^{-21} vs. -2.0×10^{-22}), suggesting that PLA: PCL blends can

decrease the release rate of hydrophobic IMC, but not for hydrophilic TCH due to their enhanced interaction. Furthermore, the decrease in k_{off} values of IMC, when compared with TCH (from 0.0033 to 0.0025 h^{-1}), indicates a stronger interaction between the drug and carrier.

Table 2: Drug release parameters obtained by fitting drug release data to five different models of drug release kinetics.

Model	Zero order	First order	Higuchi	Ritger-Peppas	Zeng
Equation	$Mt/M_\infty = K_0 t$	$Mt/M_\infty = 1 - e^{-K_1 t}$	$Mt/M_\infty = K_H t^{1/2}$	$Mt/M_\infty = K_R t^n$	**
PLA: PCL /IMC	$K_0=0.002$ $R^2=0.564$	$K_1=0.436$ $R^2=0.822$	$K_H=0.037$ $R^2=0.801$	$K_R=1.618$ $n=0.251$ $R^2=0.938$	$K_{on}=0.0049 \text{ h}^{-1}$ $K_{off}=0.0025 \text{ h}^{-1}$ $K_s=1.006 \text{ h}^{-1}$ $\Delta G = -2.1 \times 10^{-21} \text{ J}$ $R^2=0.945$
PLA: PCL /TCH	$K_0=0.002$ $R^2=0.434$	$K_1=0.582$ $R^2=0.839$	$K_H=0.038$ $R^2=0.691$	$K_R=1.262$ $n=0.204$ $R^2=0.927$	$K_{on}=0.0034 \text{ h}^{-1}$ $K_{off}=0.0033 \text{ h}^{-1}$ $K_s=1.160 \text{ h}^{-1}$ $\Delta G = -2.0 \times 10^{-22} \text{ J}$ $R^2=0.920$
PLA: PCL / HNT-ASP / TCH	$K_0=0.0012$ $R^2=0.314$	$K_1=0.857$ $R^2=0.961$	$K_H=0.024$ $R^2=0.534$	$K_R=2.025$ $n=0.323$ $R^2=0.684$	$K_{on}=0.0012 \text{ h}^{-1}$ $K_{off}=0.00068 \text{ h}^{-1}$ $K_s=1.025 \text{ h}^{-1}$ $\Delta G = -2.2 \times 10^{-21} \text{ J}$ $R^2=0.986$

$$** M_t/M_\infty = [K_{off}/(K_{on} + K_{off})](1 - e^{-K_s t}) + [K_{on}/(K_{on} + K_{off})](1 - e^{-K_{off} t})$$

* $\Delta G = -k_B T \ln(K_{on}/K_{off})$, where k_B is the Boltzmann's constant and T is the absolute temperature (300 K).

Moreover, by embedding HNT-ASP to nanofibers, there was a small change detected in K_s while ΔG decreased from -2.0×10^{-22} to $-2.2 \times 10^{-21} \text{ J}$. Such results confirm that embedded HNT-ASP decreases the TCH release and overcomes the fast release caused by the poor interaction between loaded TCH and PLA: PCL blends. This lies in the interaction between TCH molecules and HNT-ASP producing hydrogen bonds with the silanol groups on the HNT-ASP. The TCH release might not completely fit these models because these models do not take into account the erosion/biodegradation and dimensional alteration of the drug carrier. However, the results obtained from Zeng model are in good agreement

with what has been obtained through the experimental results.

4 Conclusions

It has been found that the addition of TCH appears to increase electrical conductivity of PLA: PCL blend solution, thus considerably decrease the average nanofiber diameters. Nonetheless, the nanofiber diameters were found not to be changed remarkably by adding IMC. TCH and IMC loading can contribute to the decreasing tendencies in the degree of crystallinity, T_g and T_m values of PCL within the PLA: PCL blends. FTIR spectra confirm the successful encapsulation of IMC and TCH to the PLA: PCL blends and nanocomposites. Loading a hydrophilic drug (TCH) into HNT-ASP and hydrophobic polymer blends (PLA: PCL) was detected to decrease drug release and overcome the weak interaction between the PLA: PCL blends and TCH drug. This typical characteristic was clearly revealed with excellent agreement between obtained experimental data and Ritger-Peppas model and Zeng model in understanding the mechanism of drug release kinetics.

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